

One pot synthesis and fungicidal activity of some bis-(2-arylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane by electrolytic initiated desulfurization of propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone[†]

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Abstract : A facile and efficient route for synthesis of substituted bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been carried out at platinum electrode from electrocyclization of propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone by using LiClO₄ as supporting electrolyte in acetonitrile as non-aqueous solvent under controlled potential electrolysis at room temperature. The synthesized compounds were characterized by spectroscopic methods and mechanism was deduced from cyclic voltammetric studies. The fungicidal activities of products (6a-6f) were evaluated against fungal strain *Aspergillus flavus* and *Alternaria solani*. Excellent yields with high atom economy, shortest reaction time and easy work-up are attractive features in context to green chemistry.

Keywords : Bis-oxadiazoles, controlled potential electrolysis, environmentally benign, electrochemical synthesis, cation radical, Green chemistry.

Introduction

The 1,3,4-oxadiazole and their derivatives constitute an important class of organic compounds with diverse agricultural, industrial and biological activities. 1,3,4-Oxadiazole scaffold is established as a member of the privileged structural class particularly from a medicinal point of view. Its having a wide range of biological activities such as antibacterial¹, anti HIV¹, antifungal², genotoxic², antituberculosis³, virucidal⁴, antimalarial⁵, insecticidal⁶, herbicidal⁷, analgesic⁸, anti-inflammatory⁹, muscle relaxants¹⁰, anticonvulsant¹¹, sedative, hypnotic¹², anticancer¹³ and lipid peroxidation inhibitor¹⁴. Due to their metabolic profile, improved pharmacokinetics and *in vivo* performance they are recognized as biologically important pharmacophores¹⁵.

It seems that this electrochemical procedure will emerge as new tool where the special advantages of the electrochemistry such as energy specificity, chemical selectivity and specific activation of small molecules can be applied without toxic reagents and solvents. Electrochemical reactions offer a clean route to the formation of anion and

cation radical species from neutral organic molecules by movement of electron. Electrons can be added or removed from the substrates under mild conditions without using oxidizing or reducing reagents which might complicate the reaction sequence¹⁶. A major advantage of electrochemical methods is the reduced formation of side products.

In the present investigation we reported a series of substituted bis-1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives which were synthesized from oxidative electrocyclization of different propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone, evaluation of their antifungal activity, and also developed a simple, facile, environmentally benign protocol for the synthesis of bio-dynamic heterocyclic compounds we describe here.

Results and discussion

Although numerous procedures are enumerated in literature for the synthesis of oxadiazoles, most of them suffer a major setback from the standpoint of environmental concerns as many of them usually carried out in various synthetic steps that require very dangerous re-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

agents such as bromine or full equivalent of Hg^{II} and produce undesirable mercury by products which must be removed and properly disposed off after the reaction is completed. In conventional protocol include bromine oxidation of semicarbazide derivative and the cyclodesulfurization of acylthiosemicarbazide derivatives in solution using I_2/NaOH or 1,3-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC)¹⁷⁻¹⁹, as well as mercury(II) acetate ($\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$) or yellow mercury(II) oxide HgO^{20-23} . Not only handling of these reagents is difficult but also very hazardous to the environment. From the first step to last step of the reaction including extraction and purification of the product demands great precautions.

With increasing public concern over environmental degradation, use of electrochemical technology can provide a valuable alternative to the conventional reagents for fine chemical synthesis. Due to the electron transfer between an electrode and the substrate molecules the formation of highly reactive intermediates are achieved under mild condition, avoiding acid and bases as reducing or oxidizing agent and related waste by-products.

Keeping that objective in mind, we synthesized some bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (**6a-6f**) by anodic mediated cyclization of propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (**5a-5f**) at the platinum electrode. This electrochemical cyclization gave the oxadiazoles (Scheme 1) without requirement of any hazardous reagents. Acetonitrile was used as a solvent and lithium perchlorate (LiClO_4) as supporting electro-

lyte which can be handled easily without major precautions.

The objective of our research programme is to find a new environmentally benign preparation of bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles, in which the use of toxic reagents could be minimized. Proposed mechanism in Scheme 2 show that propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone undergoes two electron oxidation confirmed by cyclic voltammetry in Fig. 1 followed by dehydrosulphidation to form bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles.

Experimental

Instruments :

The electrochemical synthesis was performed in 50 mL three-electrode cell assembly with platinum plate (flattened sheet with dimension of 1.0 cm \times 1.0 cm), counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. Cyclic voltammetry was performed using ALSCH instruments electrochemical analyzer Model 600 A.

^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were obtained on Bruker DRX (400 MHz) spectrometer in CDCl_3 and TMS as internal standards (chemical shifts in δ ppm). IR spectra were registered with a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrometer in KBr pellets. Mass spectra were obtained by EI method with Shimadzu GCMS-QP5050A. The elemental analysis was done on Elemental Vario EL III. Column chromatography was carried out by using Merck silica

Scheme 1

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Scheme 2

gel 60. The purity of the synthesized compounds were confirmed by TLC on pre-coated silica gel plates in various solvent system using iodine vapors and UV light as detecting agents.

Chemicals and reagents :

All the chemicals used were of synthetic and AR grade and was procured from Agros-Organics, USA, S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Mumbai and Merck, Mumbai, India. These chemicals were used without further purification. All experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Electro-organic synthesis of 6a-6f :

Acylhydrazine **3** was prepared by dissolving hydrazine hydrate **2** and diethyl ester **1** (diethyl glutarate) in 2 : 1 ratio with continuous stirring. The mixture was left overnight which evolved a solid product **3**. Equimolar amount of acylhydrazine **3** and phenylisothiocyanate **4** mixed in a small beaker with continuous stirring evolved a solid product propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone **5** which was used as initial compound for the electrolysis.

Electrolysis :

In a typical procedure, 50 mL mixture of acetonitrile containing propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone (0.271 g, 1.0 mmol) and supporting electrolyte LiClO₄ (0.16 g, 1.0 mmol) were added to the electrolytic cell. Preparative scale controlled potential electrolysis²⁴⁻²⁷ were carried out at corresponding oxidation potentials of the substrates and were completed in 3 to 4 h until no oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. All the products were solid, colored and entirely different from the starting compound. The current potential data

was recorded with the help of potentiostat at the interval of 15 min as depicted in Table 1.

The electrocyclization of **5a** was carried out in acetonitrile at constant potential of 2.1 V using LiClO₄ as supporting electrolyte. The electricity used for the electrolysis was very small as compared to other conventional methods. Progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. When the reaction was completed, supporting electrolyte was removed by silica gel column chromatography. The products were isolated by silica gel column chromatography (CHCl₃ : H₂O, 1 : 1 v/v).

Electrochemical study of propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone 5a :

Cyclic voltammograms of propylenediacylthiosemicarbazone **5a** has been studied in acetonitrile solution containing 0.1 M lithium perchlorate are shown in Fig. 1.

Characterization of the products :

Bis-(2-phenyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane (6a) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.46–7.01 (10H, m), 3.98 (2H, s), 2.53 (4H, m), 1.97 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) : δ 115–146.7, 29.7, 29.7, 33.6; IR (KBr) : 3421, 2921, 1594, 1242, 1028.

Bis-(2-methoxyphenyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane (6b) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.35–6.57 (8H, m), 3.98 (2H, s), 2.53 (4H, m), 1.97 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.73 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) : δ 116–148.6, 29.7, 29.7, 33.6, 56.0; IR (KBr) : 3414, 2924, 1599, 1256, 1026.

Table 1. Current-potential and yield data of bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles **6a-6f**

Sl. No.	Substrate	N	R	Product	Time (min)	Applied potential ^a (V)	Current (A)	Yield ^b (%)
1.	5a	3	C ₆ H ₅ -	6a	190	2.10	0.54	81
2.	5b	3	2-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	6b	200	2.54	0.51	89
3.	5c	3	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	6c	200	2.74	0.61	90
4.	5d	3	3-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	6d	180	2.77	0.46	91
5.	5e	3	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	6e	230	2.21	0.69	72
6.	5f	3	C ₁₀ H ₇ -	6f	210	2.24	0.45	73

^aApplied potential of the substrates. ^bYield of the product.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of **5a** in 0.1 M LiClO₄ at platinum electrode (area 1 × 1 cm²) at scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹, counter electrode; platinum mesh, reference electrode; Ag/AgCl, t = 25 ± 1 °C. The corresponding cyclic voltammetry exhibit two anodic peaks within range 2.0–3.0 V. These peaks represent two electron oxidation process.

Bis-(4-methoxyphenyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane (**6c**) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.35–6.57 (8H, m), 3.98 (2H, s), 2.53 (4H, m), 1.97 (2H, m), 3.73 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) : δ 114.9–152.0, 29.7, 29.7, 33.6, 56.0; IR (KBr) : 3359, 2924, 2839, 1614,

1256, 1026.

Bis-(3-methylphenyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane (**6d**) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.32–6.82 (8H, m), 3.98 (2H, s), 2.53 (4H, m, CH₂), 1.97 (2H, m), 2.53 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) : δ 112.0–146.6,

Table 2. Antifungal screening results of the products (**6a-6f**)^a

Compound	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>			<i>Alternaria solani</i>		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
6a	76	47	25	62	38	18
6b	89	70	48	90	72	48
6c	96	74	51	94	75	54
6d	60	36	19	64	39	18
6e	66	41	20	65	40	20
6f	53	22	12	50	22	9
Dithane M-45	100	83	63	100	85	66

^aAverage inhibition of fungal growth (%) at stated concentration (mg/L⁻¹).

29.7, 29.7, 33.6, 20.9; IR (KBr) : 3359, 2924, 2839, 1614, 1256, 1026.

Bis-(4-methylphenyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane (6e) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.32–6.82 (8H, m), 3.98 (2H, s), 2.53 (4H, m), 1.97 (2H, m), 2.53 (6H, s); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) : δ 112.0–146.6, 29.7, 29.7, 33.6, 20.9; IR (KBr) : 3359, 2924, 2839, 1614, 1256, 1026.

Bis-(N-naphthylphenyl amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)propane (6g) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) : δ 6.55–7.66 (14H, m), 3.98 (1H, s), 2.53 (4H, m), 1.97 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) : δ 109.4–142.0, 29.7, 29.7, 33.6, IR (KBr) : 3359, 2922, 2839, 1617, 1258, 1030.

Evaluation of antifungal activity :

Detail of antifungal assays :

The fungicidal activity of product **6a-6f** was evaluated against fungal strain *Aspergillus flavus*, *Alternaria solani* by usual agar growth technique^{28,29} at 10, 100, 1000 ppm concentration. Dithane M-45 as standard commercial fungicide was also tested under similar condition for comparison. The numbers of replicate assays were three, and six replicate controls were used and no remarkable morphological changes were observed in the developing fungi. The test fungi were inoculated in the centre of the petridishes and incubated at 28 ± 1 °C for 96 h. After this time the percent inhibition of the mycelia growth compared with that in control dishes was recorded and result thus were summarized in Table 2.

Conclusion

A new, facile and efficient methodology for eco-compatible preparation of substituted bis-1,3,4-oxadiazoles via one pot controlled potential anodic mediated electrocyclization of propylenediacylthiosemicarbazones has been developed in our laboratory. All the synthesized compounds exhibited significant antifungal activity against the tested fungi. The mildness of the electrooxidation, experimental simplicity, compatibility with various functional groups, excellent product yield, shorter reaction time, and the easy work-up procedure make this approach more attractive in synthesizing a variety of such derivatives.

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